

DOES POVERTY AFFECT THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SCHEDULED CASTE HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Cite This Article: A. Xavier Joseph & Dr. R. Arumugarajan, "Does Poverty Affect the Socio-Economic Development of Scheduled Caste Higher Secondary Students", *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education*, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 415-421, 2018.

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Abstract:

The socio-economic status of an individual or a community is influenced by multiple factors. This study attempts to find out whether the factor 'poverty' affects the socio-economic development of scheduled caste higher secondary students. Survey method was adopted for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used for collecting a sample of 715 higher secondary students from 79 schools in Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu State, India. The applied statistical techniques percentage analysis, 't' test, ANOVA, Pearson's product moment correlation, regression analysis and factor analysis revealed the following results. The level of poverty of majority of the SC higher secondary students was found to be moderate. A significant difference was found between male and female SC higher secondary students in their poverty, and the female SC higher secondary students were better than the male SC higher secondary students in their poverty. A significant difference was found among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their poverty. The private school SC higher secondary students were better in their poverty than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students. A significant relationship and influence were found between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students. The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of poverty with considerable factor loading.

Key Words: Poverty, Socio-Economic Status & Higher Secondary Students

Introduction:

Education of a child has been under the influence of various factors and it is rather difficult to say which factor has more influence than the other factors, unless it is researched upon. The Indian social system is caste based. "Caste is a powerful organization in Indian society" (Kaur, 2015). and it has its own influence in the education system. "The state and place of the Scheduled Castes was very critical in ancient and in medieval periods. But when the Western ruler held the power in India, the position of the Scheduled Castes was improved. Their status has still improving due to constitutional provisions" (Behera, 2015). Beginning from school admission till the employment entry, caste system is followed officially, as per the norms and guidelines of the government of India. This is primarily to improve the socio-economic status of the SC community. In this context, this study attempts to find out the level of poverty of SC higher secondary students; and the relationship with and influence of poverty on the socio-economic status, as the results could be used to improve the SC community.

Significance of the Study:

Higher secondary school education plays an important role in deciding the professional carrier in an individual. It is after this course these students choose and enter into the streamlined specific educational field that forms the basis of their future life. Considering this, the students, the teacher, the parents and the school management puts in so many efforts to produce better results at the higher secondary level. Higher secondary education has almost become a basic qualification for employment at all formal levels. India, being a country that follows the caste system, adheres to the quota system in studies and employment based on the caste. Scheduled Caste (SC) is considered to be the lowest caste in the Indian caste system and their socio-economic status is considered to be poor. The government of India, since independence, has been implementing various schemes and offering multiple concessions to bring them up socially, economically and educationally. "Social and economic justice, equality of status and opportunities and cultural and educational status are insured by the Constitution of India for all citizens and also provide enriched provisions for scheduled caste and tribes" (Jeyakumar & Palaniyammal, 2016). "The Indian society is based on a caste system with vast inequalities in social, political, economic and educational spheres" (Barman, 2014). "The social and economic deprivation among Scheduled Castes had been most common during pre and post-Independence" (Singh, 2014). "The educational backwardness of the Dalit communities is generally attributed to poverty and illiterate home environments prevailing among them" (Nambissan, 1996). It is at this background, with a sense of social commitment and interest, the investigator being a teacher, attempts to find out the relationship between and

impact of poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students. As the study is of much social relevance and benefits, the investigator has undertaken this research whether poverty affects the socio-economic development of scheduled caste higher secondary students. No such study has been undertaken so far, and so this study becomes a need and significant.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the level of poverty of higher secondary students
- ✓ To find out the level of poverty of higher secondary students with respect to (i) gender, (ii) students residence, (iii) type of school and (iv) nature of school.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between (i) male and female; (ii) rural and urban higher secondary students in their poverty
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference among (i) government, aided and private; and (ii) boys, girls and co-education school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant relationship between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant influence of poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant factor with positive loading of the variable poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between rural and urban area SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students
- ✓ There is no significant influence of poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is no significant factor with positive loading of the variable poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Methodology:

The investigator used survey method of research in this study. “Survey refers to the method of securing information concerning a phenomena under study from all or a selected number of respondents of the concerned universe” (Kothari, 2004). Simple random sampling was used to choose the sample from the population. A total sample of 715 higher secondary students, studying in higher secondary schools, was selected for the study. Among the 715 samples, 219 were drawn from Kuzhithurai, 244 were from Thuckalay and 252 were from Nagercoil educational districts of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India. The investigator used 2 tools in the present study: (1) An inventory constructed and standardized by the investigator to identify the factor poverty of SC higher secondary students, and (2) The adapted tool of the Revised Socio Economic Status Scale for Urban and Rural India, by Kuppaswamy (2015). The statistical analysis Percentage analysis, differential analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis and factor analysis were used for analyzing the data.

Analysis of Data:

Percentage Analysis:

Objective 1:

To find out the level of poverty of SC higher secondary students.

Table 1: Level of Poverty of SC Higher Secondary Students

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Poverty	169	23.6	392	54.9	154	21.5

It is inferred from the above table that 23.6% of SC higher secondary students have low, 54.9% of them have moderate and 21.5% of them have high level of poverty. This has been shown in the Figure 1.

Objective 2:

To find out the level of poverty of SC higher secondary students with respect to gender.

Table 2: Level of Poverty of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Gender

Variable	Gender	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Poverty	Male	99	26.1	204	53.8	76	20.1
	Female	70	20.8	188	56.0	78	23.2

It is inferred from the above table that 26.1% of male SC higher secondary students have low, 53.8% of them have moderate and 20.1% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the female SC higher secondary students, 20.8% of them have low, 56.0% of them have moderate and 23.2% of them have high level of poverty. This has been shown in the Figure 2.

Objective 3:

To find out the level of poverty of SC higher secondary students with respect to their residence.

Table 3: Level of Poverty of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Students Residence

Variable	Students Residence	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Poverty	Rural	125	24.4	286	55.8	102	19.8
	Urban	44	21.8	106	52.5	52	25.7

It is inferred from the above table that 24.4% of rural area SC higher secondary students have low, 55.8% of them have moderate and 19.8% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the urban area SC higher secondary students, 21.8% of them have low, 52.5% of them have moderate and 25.7% of them have high level of poverty. This has been shown in the figure 3.

Objective 4:

To find out the level of poverty SC higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table 4: Level of Poverty of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Type of School

Variable	Type of the School	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Poverty	Government	77	24.1	207	64.7	36	11.2
	Aided	82	25.9	152	48.2	82	25.9
	Private	10	12.7	33	41.8	36	45.5

It is inferred from the above table that 24.1% of government school SC higher secondary students have low, 64.7% of them have moderate and 11.2% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the aided school SC higher secondary students, 25.9% of them have low, 48.2% of them have moderate and 25.9% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the private school SC higher secondary students, 12.7% of them have low, 41.8% of them have moderate and 45.5% of them have high level of poverty. This has been shown in the Figure 4.

Objective 5:

To find out the level of poverty of SC higher secondary students with respect to nature of the school.

Table 5: Level of Poverty of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Nature of the School

Variable	Nature of the School	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Poverty	Boys	10	30.3	15	45.5	8	24.2
	Girls	11	14.5	58	76.3	7	9.2
	Co-education	148	24.4	319	52.7	139	22.9

It is inferred from the above table that 30.3% of boys school SC higher secondary students have low, 45.5% of them have moderate and 24.2% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the girls school SC higher secondary students, 14.5% of them have low, 76.3% of them have moderate and 9.2% of them have high level of poverty. Regarding the co-education school SC higher secondary students, 24.4% of them have low, 52.7% of them have moderate and 22.9% of them have high level of poverty. This has been shown in the Figure 5.

Differential Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their

poverty.

Table 6: Difference between Male and Female SC Higher Secondary Students in their Poverty

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Poverty	Male	379	18.82	5.608	2.35	S
	Female	336	19.76	5.004		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, S - Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (2.35) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their poverty. While comparing the mean scores of male (Mean=18.82) and female SC higher secondary students (Mean=19.76), the female SC higher secondary students are better than the male SC higher secondary students in their poverty. This has been shown in the Figure 6.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference between rural and urban area SC higher secondary students in their poverty.

Table 7: Difference between Rural and Urban Area SC Higher Secondary Students in their Poverty

Variable	Students Residence	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Poverty	Rural	513	19.07	5.261	1.54	NS
	Urban	202	19.76	5.551		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (1.54) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between rural and urban area SC higher secondary students in their poverty.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.

Table 8: Difference among Boys, Girls and Co-education School SC Higher Secondary Students in their Poverty

Variable	Source of variation	df (2, 712)		Calculated 'F' value	Remark
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Poverty	Between	45.589	22.795	0.79	NS
	Within	20387.921	28.635		

(For (2, 712) df the table value of 'F' is 3.00, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (0.79) is less than the table value (3.00) for the df 2, 712 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.

Table 9: Difference among Government, Aided and Private School SC Higher Secondary Students in their Poverty

Variable	Source of variation	df (2, 712)		Calculated 'F' value	Remark
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Poverty	Between	734.510	367.255	13.27	S
	Within	19699.000	27.667		

(For (2, 712) df the table value of 'F' is 3.00, S - Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (13.27) is greater than the table value (3.00) for the df 2, 712 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their poverty. Scheffe test is used as post hoc test to find which of the paired mean scores differ significantly.

Table 9 (a): Scheffe Test Showing the Mean Difference in Poverty with Respect to Type of the School

Type of the School	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Government	320	18.53	
Aided	316	19.35	
Private	79		21.92

The Scheffe post hoc test result from the above table indicates that the private school SC higher secondary students are better in their poverty than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students. This has been shown in the figure 6.

Correlational Analysis:

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 10: Relationship between Poverty and Socio-Economic Status of SC Higher Secondary Students

Variables	N	df	Table 'γ' value	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks
Poverty and Socio-Economic Status	716	714	0.063	0.255	S

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'γ' value (0.255) is greater than the table value (0.063) for the df 714 at 0.05 level of significance. As the result shows that there is significant relationship between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students, the respective null hypothesis is rejected.

Regression Analysis:

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant influence of poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 11 (a): Regression Analysis: Socio-Economic Status

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.288 ^a	.083	.074	3.933

The above regression table summarizes the model performance with relevant analysis. R represents the multiple correlation coefficient with a range lies between -1 and +1. Since the R value is 0.288, it means socio-economic status percentage has a positive relationship with poverty of SC higher secondary students.

R square represents the coefficient of determination and ranges between 0 and 1. Since the R square value is 0.083, 8% of the variation in socio-economic status is enhanced poverty of SC higher secondary students.

Table 11 (b): ANOVA – Socio-Economic Status

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	987.436	7	141.062	9.119	.000 ^b
	Residual	10936.620	707	15.469		

Total	11924.056	714		
a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Status				
b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty				

From the above ANOVA table 'F' value is significant (significant value is less than 0.05) it means dependent variable socio-economic status is more reliable.

Table 11(c): Regression Model - Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	't' Value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	β		
1	(Constant)	6.960	1.160		5.999	.000
	Poverty	.195	.031	.256	6.299	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Status

The above regression model coefficient table reports the coefficients for poverty helps to improve Socio-Economic Status significantly. The model coefficients are used in the construction of regression equation. The regression equation for the above data is: Socio-Economic Status percentage = 6.960 (constant) + 0.195 (Poverty). From the regression equation, it is observed that poverty has a positive influence on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Factor Analysis:

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant factor with positive loading of the variable poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 12: Factor Loading of Poverty on Socio-Economic Status of SC higher secondary students

Variable	Factor Loading	Nature of Variables
Poverty	.665	Considerable presence

The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of poverty with considerable factor loading (.665).

Major Findings and Conclusion:

- ✓ There is significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their poverty, and the female SC higher secondary students are better than the male SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is no significant difference (i) between rural and urban area, and (ii) among boys, girls and co-education school SC higher secondary students in their poverty.
- ✓ There is significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their poverty. The private school SC higher secondary students are better in their poverty than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between poverty and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is significant influence of poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of poverty with considerable factor loading.

Based on these findings, it could be inferentially and statistically concluded that poverty is one of the factors that affect the socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students. However, it could be further confirmed as the study is limited to the geographical location of Kanyakumari district in Tamil Nadu State alone.

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